

Deliverable D.7.5

Report on the Standardization landscape and applicable standards

Date: 2024-12-16

Version: 1

**Funded by
the European Union**

SOIL O-LIVE (Grant Agreement ID: 101091255) is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EIC. Neither the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable 7.5 Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards

Document Information

Project title	SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES
Project acronym	SOIL O-LIVE
Grant Agreement	101091255
Work package	WP7 - Outreach, dissemination and communication
Deliverable number and title	D.7.5 Standardization landscape
Deliverable description	Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards
Deliverable type	R
Dissemination level	PU
Lead beneficiary	UNE
Due submission date	30 June 2023 (M6)
Submission date	16 February 2025

Document Author(s) and Reviewer(s)

Name	Entity	Role (author, reviewer)
Rosa Cepas Aguayo	UNE	Author
Ivan Sánchez	UJA	Reviewer

Document history

Version	Date	Made by	Short Description of Changes
V0	2023-06-27	Rosa Cepas Aguayo	First version
V1	2024-12-16	Rosa Cepas Aguayo	Format update

Table of Contents

Document Information.....	1
Executive Summary	3
1. Introduction	4
1.1. Purpose of the document	4
1.2. Project presentation overview	4
1.3. Short introduction about standardization.....	4
2. Methodology.....	8
3. Standardization areas relevant for SOIL O-LIVE.....	10
3.1. Technical Committees.....	10
3.2. Relevant standards for SOIL O-LIVE.....	11
3.3. Standards related to “Soil quality”	14
3.4. Sampling and sample preparation	14
3.5. Standards related to plastics and microplastics.	30
3.6. Standards related to geographic information.....	30
3.7. Standards related to oil quality.....	32
3.8. Standards related to environmental management.....	36
3.9. Standards under development	37
4. Conclusions.....	41
5. References	42
Abbreviations and acronyms.....	43
ANNEX I. Scope of the relevant standards identified	44

Executive Summary

D7.5 is the first deliverable for task T7.2 “Analysis of the applicable standardization landscape” inside WP7 “Outreach, dissemination and communication”.

It collects information on the standardization landscape to provide information for other WP, ensure compatibility and interoperability of Soil O-live and facilitate the acceptance and utilization by the market of the developed solutions.

The Spanish Association for Standardization (UNE) is part of Soil O-live Consortium and, as a National Standardization Body (NSB), its main task in the project is to provide support regarding the standardization tasks included in the project (WP7. Outreach, dissemination and communications)

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

The purpose of this report D7.5 is to provide information on the standardization landscape and applicable standards relevant for the Soil O-live project. It pretends to provide starting information for the work packages ensuring compatibility and interoperability with already existing solutions by identifying existing standards and standards under development at European and international levels in the areas that have been targeted in the project.

1.2. Project presentation overview

Soil O-LIVE aims to:

- analyze the impact of pollution and land degradation on soils from olive groves in terms of multi-biodiversity, ecological function at different levels of organization and scales;
- to investigate the relationship of soil health status with quality and safety of olive oil;
- to implement effective soil amendments and ecological restoration practices that promote manifest soil biodiversity and functionality enhancements in permanent Mediterranean olive orchards across its native range of distribution, that should be translated to improvements in olive oil quality and safety;
- to define rigorous ecological thresholds that allow to implement future clear standards and regulations in order to design a novel certification for healthy soils in European olive orchards.

1.3. Short introduction about standardization

Standards are voluntary technical documents that set out requirements for a specific item, material, component, system or service, or describes in detail a particular method, procedure or best practice. Standards are developed and defined through a process of sharing knowledge and building consensus among technical experts nominated by interested parties and other stakeholders - including businesses, consumers and environmental groups, among others. These experts are organized in Technical Committees (TCs), which are subdivided in Subcommittees (SCs) or Working Groups (WGs). These TCs are included in the structure of the Standardization Organizations (National, European and International, with the respective mirror committees) and work following their internal regulations.

The standardization bodies operate at National (UNE, AFNOR, BSI, DIN, etc.), Regional (CEN, CENELEC, ETSI) or International (ISO, IEC, ITU) level. Sometimes there are different standardization bodies at the same level, but covering different fields.

This is the case of ISO (general), IEC (electrical) and ITU (telecommunications) at international level, or CEN, CENELEC and ETSI at European level in the same way.

There are also different kinds of standardization documents. The most widespread is the standard, which has a different code depending on the organization under it was developed, e.g. EN for European Standards, ISO for International standards. Other types of documents are Technical Specifications (TS), Technical Reports (TR) and Workshop Agreements (CWA). Further Amendments to the standards are identified by adding A1, A2, etc. at the end of the standard code.

The formal definition of a standard is a “document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context”. These include requirements and/or recommendations in relation to products, systems, processes or services. European Standards (ENs) are documents that have been ratified by one of the three European Standardization Organizations (ESOs), CEN, CENELEC or ETSI; recognized as competent in the area of voluntary technical standardization as for the EU Regulation 1025/2012.

At European level, all the members of CEN shall adopt EN standards as national standards and have to withdraw any existing national standard which could conflict with them.

A summary of the characteristics of the different standardization documents can be found in the following table (Table 1)

Table 1 – Characteristics of different standardization documents

Type	International code	European code	National code	Main characteristics
Standard	ISO	EN	UNE, NF, BS, DIN, etc. When adopting: UNE-EN, NF-EN, UNE-ISO, NF-ISO, etc.	Elaboration: 3 years 2 steps of member approval European: compulsory national adoption Revision: every 5 years
Technical Specification	ISO/TS	CEN/TS	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TS, NF-CEN/TS, UNE-ISO/TS, NF-ISO/TS, etc.	Elaboration: 21 months 1 step of member approval or internal approval in TC European: optional national adoption Revision: at 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)
Technical Report	ISO/TR	CEN/TR	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TR, NF-CEN/TR, UNE-ISO/TR, NF-ISO/TR, etc.	Elaboration: free timeframe Internal approval in TC European: optional national adoption No revision required
Workshop Agreement	IWA	CWA	Variable	Elaboration: free timeframe (usually few months) Internal approval in the Workshop European: optional national adoption Revision: at 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)

European and International Standardization Organizations (e.g. CEN and ISO) have signed formal agreements in order to avoid duplication of efforts and promote global relevance of standards, which allows to adopt or develop in parallel each other's standards with the same content and code.

The technical collaboration between ISO and CEN was formalized through the Vienna Agreement (VA).

European standards developed through the Vienna Agreement have EN ISO codification while International Standards developed through the Vienna Agreement remain only with ISO code.

National standards could also be proposed as a base for new European or International standards.

The following Figure 1 shows the possible tracks of the standards.

Figure 1 – Possible tracks of standards adoption

Therefore, the code of any standard is the combination of the above mentioned issues, and could be explained as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Example of identification of elements in the code of a standard

2. Methodology

For the identification of standards and standards under development relevant for SOIL O-LIVE project the following methodology has been followed:

1. A list of key concepts was prepared to act as a starting point for the identification of standardization areas.
2. For the selection of the key concepts the aims and goals of the project and the levels in which the project should integrate were taken into account. Also the needs of the use cases were considered..

**Table 2. List of key concepts acting as a starting point
for the identification of standardization areas for SOIL O-LIVE**

Key concept
1. Soil
2. Soil quality
3. Soil sampling
4. Soil chemical and physical characterization
5. Soil chemical contaminants
6. Pesticides and herbicides residues
7. Microplastics
8. Soil biodiversity (flora, fauna, microbiology)
9. Soil remediation
10. Soil data management
11. Climate change
12. Geographic information
13. Oil quality
14. Environmental management

3. Both already published standards and standards under development were identified for each standardization area, together with the technical committee responsible for the respective standards.

The search covered the European standardization developed by the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) and international standardization developed by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO).

Also, considering that the International Olive Council develops documents that could be interesting for the project (some of them have been later adopted as standards at ISO level) the search has also included its database.

The databases and websites used for the search are referred in Clause 5.

4. As a result of the searching process a first draft has been prepared by UNE including 252 developed standards and standards under development and 8 technical bodies. Also information about some relevant standards has been provided to SOIL O-LIVE partners as an input.
5. As a final stage, SOIL O-LIVE partners will be asked to identify those references that really should be considered for the project, specifying in what WP it would be used, how the standard would influence/impact the project implementations and risks/opportunities from technical and business perspective.
6. As a result of all the process described above a list of standards relevant for SOIL O-LIVE has been identified (see clause 3.2).

3. Standardization areas relevant for SOIL O-LIVE

3.1. Technical Committees

The following table (Table 3) includes a list of the European (CEN/TC) and International (ISO/TC) that have been identified as relevant for several of the items included in the list of key concepts (Table 2.)

Table 3. European and International Technical Committees related to SOIL O-LIVE

Area	Technical Committee
Soil	CEN/TC 444 “Test methods for environmental characterization of solid matrices”
	ISO/TC 190 “Soil quality”
Microplastics	CEN/TC 249 “Plastics”
	ISO /TC 61/SC 14 “Plastics. Environmental aspects”
Geographic information	ISO/TC 211 “Geographic information/Geomatics”
Oil quality	CEN/TC 307 “Oilseeds, vegetable and animal fats and oils and their by-products - Methods of sampling and analysis”
	ISO/TC 34/SC 11 “Animal and vegetable fats and oils”
Environmental management	ISO/TC 207 “Environmental management”

3.2. Relevant standards for SOIL O-LIVE

The following table (Table 4.1 and 4.2) includes a list of standards already published or in development, even European (EN) as international (ISO) that have been identified as key standards. These references have been extracted from the following subclauses (3.3 to 3.8)

.Its scope is included in ANNEX I

Table 4.1 Relevant standards identified for SOIL O-LIVE. Standards already published.

Reference	Title
ISO 18400-205:2018	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 205: Guidance on the procedure for investigation of natural, near-natural and cultivated sites
ISO 11264:2005	Soil quality — Determination of herbicides — Method using HPLC with UV-detection
ISO 10694:1995	Soil quality — Determination of organic and total carbon after dry combustion (elementary analysis)
ISO 10382:2002	Soil quality — Determination of organochlorine pesticides and polychlorinated biphenyls — Gas-chromatographic method with electron capture detection
ISO 11063:2020	Soil quality — Direct extraction of soil DNA
ISO 14240-1:1997	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial biomass — Part 1: Substrate-induced respiration method
ISO 14240-2:1997	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial biomass — Part 2: Fumigation-extraction method
ISO/TS 10832:2009	Soil quality — Effects of pollutants on mycorrhizal fungi — Spore germination test
ISO 21286:2019	Soil quality — Identification of ecotoxicological test species by DNA barcoding

Reference	Title
ISO 18504:2017	Soil quality — Sustainable remediation
ISO 19152:2012	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM)
ISO 24363:2023	Determination of fatty acid methyl esters (<i>cis</i> and <i>trans</i>) and squalene in olive oil and other vegetable oils by gas chromatography
ISO 12871:2019	Olive oils and olive-pomace oils — Determination of aliphatic and triterpenic alcohols content by capillary gas chromatography
ISO 12872:2022	Olive oils and olive-pomace oils — Determination of the 2-glyceryl monopalmitate content
ISO 12873:2010	Olive oils and olive-pomace oils — Determination of wax content by capillary gas chromatography
COI/T.20/Doc. No 15	Sensory analysis of olive oil – method for the organoleptic assessment of virgin olive oil
ISO 14055-1:2017	Environmental management — Guidelines for establishing good practices for combatting land degradation and desertification — Part 1: Good practices framework
ISO/TR 14055-2:2022	Environmental management — Guidelines for establishing good practices for combatting land degradation and desertification — Part 2: Regional case studies

Table 4.2 Relevant standards identified for SOIL O-LIVE. Standards under development

Reference	Title
ISO/AWI 18721	Assessment of ecological soil functions: indicators and methods
ISO/NP 19254	Simultaneous determination of multi-class pesticide residues in soil using GC-MS/MS and LC-MS/MS analysis
ISO/FDIS 24187	Principles for the analysis of microplastics present in the environment
ISO/CD 19152-2	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 2: Land registration
ISO/CD 19152-4	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 4: Valuation information
ISO/CD 19152-5	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 5: Spatial plan information
ISO/DIS 19152-1	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 1: Generic Conceptual Model
ISO/PWI 19152-6	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 6: Part 6: Implementation aspects

3.3. Standards related to “Soil quality”.

European standards on “Soil Quality” are being developed by **CEN/TC 444 “Test methods for environmental characterization of solid matrices”**, where the standardization of methods for the environmental characterization of soil, solid and liquid waste, biowaste and sludge is defined.

The international committee **ISO/TC 190 “Soil quality”**, covers the Standardization in the field of soil quality, including soils in situ, soil materials intended for reuse of soils, including dredged sub-aquatic soil materials.

3.4. Sampling and sample preparation

Reference	Title
ISO 18512:2007	Soil quality — Guidance on long and short term storage of soil samples
ISO 16133:2018	Soil quality — Guidance on the establishment and maintenance of monitoring programmes
ISO 23909:2008	Soil quality — Preparation of laboratory samples from large samples
ISO 16720:2005	Soil quality — Pretreatment of samples by freeze-drying for subsequent analysis
ISO 14507:2003	Soil quality — Pretreatment of samples for determination of organic contaminants
ISO 11464:2006	Soil quality — Pretreatment of samples for physico-chemical analysis
ISO 18400-100:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 100: Guidance on the selection of sampling standards
ISO 18400-101:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 101: Framework for the preparation and application of a sampling plan
ISO 18400-102:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 102: Selection and application of sampling techniques
ISO 18400-103:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 103: Safety

Reference	Title
ISO 18400-104:2018	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 104: Strategies
ISO 18400-105:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 105: Packaging, transport, storage and preservation of samples
ISO 18400-106:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 106: Quality control and quality assurance
ISO 18400-107:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 107: Recording and reporting
ISO 18400-201:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 201: Physical pretreatment in the field
ISO 18400-202:2018	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 202: Preliminary investigations
ISO 18400-203:2018	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 203: Investigation of potentially contaminated sites
ISO 18400-205:2018	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 205: Guidance on the procedure for investigation of natural, near-natural and cultivated sites

3.4.1. Chemical and physical characterization

Reference	Title
EN 15309:2007	Characterization of waste and soil - Determination of elemental composition by X-ray fluorescence
EN 16170:2016	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of elements using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES)
EN 16171:2016	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of elements using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)

Reference	Title
EN 16169:2012	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of Kjeldahl nitrogen
CEN/TS 15937:2013	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of specific electrical conductivity
EN 16168:2012	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of total nitrogen using dry combustion method
EN 16173:2012	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Digestion of nitric acid soluble fractions of elements
EN 15934:2012	Sludge, treated biowaste, soil and waste - Calculation of dry matter fraction after determination of dry residue or water content
ISO 11047:1998	Soil quality — Determination of cadmium, chromium, cobalt, copper, lead, manganese, nickel and zinc — Flame and electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometric methods
ISO 10693:1995	Soil quality — Determination of carbonate content — Volumetric method
ISO 11272:2017	Soil quality — Determination of dry bulk density
ISO 11260:2018	Soil quality — Determination of effective cation exchange capacity and base saturation level using barium chloride solution
ISO 17312:2005	Soil quality — Determination of hydraulic conductivity of saturated porous materials using a rigid-wall permeameter
ISO 17313:2004	Soil quality — Determination of hydraulic conductivity of saturated porous materials using a flexible wall permeameter
ISO 10694:1995	Soil quality — Determination of organic and total carbon after dry combustion (elementary analysis)
ISO 11277:2020	Soil quality — Determination of particle size distribution in mineral soil material — Method by sieving and sedimentation

Reference	Title
ISO 11277:2020/DAMd 1	Soil quality — Determination of particle size distribution in mineral soil material — Method by sieving and sedimentation — Amendment 1
ISO 11263:1994	Soil quality — Determination of phosphorus — Spectrometric determination of phosphorus soluble in sodium hydrogen carbonate solution
ISO 11276:1995	Soil quality — Determination of pore water pressure — Tensiometer method
ISO 11271:2022	Soil quality — Determination of redox potential — Field method
ISO 16586:2003	Soil quality — Determination of soil water content as a volume fraction on the basis of known dry bulk density — Gravimetric method
ISO 16586:2003/Cor 1:2009	Soil quality — Determination of soil water content as a volume fraction on the basis of known dry bulk density — Gravimetric method — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 11275:2004	Soil quality — Determination of unsaturated hydraulic conductivity and water-retention characteristic — Wind's evaporation method
ISO 10390:2021	Soil, treated biowaste and sludge – Determination of pH
ISO 54321:2020	Soil, treated biowaste, sludge and waste — Digestion of aqua regia soluble fractions of elements
EN 15935:2021	Soil, waste, treated biowaste and sludge - Determination of loss on ignition
EN 15936:2022	Soil, waste, treated biowaste and sludge - Determination of total organic carbon (TOC) by dry combustion

3.4.2. Chemical contaminants

Reference	Title
EN 17322:2020	Environmental Solid Matrices - Determination of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB) by gas chromatography - mass selective detection (GC-MS) or electron-capture detection (GC-ECD)
CEN/TS 16182:2012	Sludge treated biowaste and soil - Determination of nonylphenols (NP) and nonylphenol-mono- and diethoxylates using gas chromatography with mass selective detection (GC-MS)
CEN/TS 16189:2012	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of linear alkylbenzene sulfonates (LAS) by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with fluorescence detection (FLD) or mass selective detection (MS)
CEN/TS 16183:2012	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of selected phthalates using capillary gas chromatography with mass spectrometric detection (GC-MS)
CEN/TS 16177:2012	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Extraction for the determination of extractable ammonia, nitrate and nitrite
ISO/TR 18105:2014	Soil quality — Detection of water soluble chromium(VI) using a ready-to-use test-kit method
ISO 16703:2004	Soil quality — Determination of content of hydrocarbon in the range C10 to C40 by gas chromatography
ISO/TS 14256-1:2003	Soil quality — Determination of nitrate, nitrite and ammonium in field-moist soils by extraction with potassium chloride solution — Part 1: Manual method
ISO 13876:2013	Soil quality — Determination of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB) by gas chromatography with mass selective detection (GC-MS) and gas chromatography with electron-capture detection (GC-ECD)

Reference	Title
ISO 18287:2006	Soil quality — Determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) — Gas chromatographic method with mass spectrometric detection (GC-MS)
ISO 13859:2014	Soil quality — Determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) by gas chromatography (GC) and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)
ISO 13913:2014	Soil quality — Determination of selected phthalates using capillary gas chromatography with mass spectrometric detection (GC/MS)
ISO/TS 16965:2013	Soil quality — Determination of trace elements using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)
ISO 15009:2016	Soil quality — Gas chromatographic determination of the content of volatile aromatic hydrocarbons, naphthalene and volatile halogenated hydrocarbons — Purge-and-trap method with thermal desorption
ISO 22155:2016	Soil quality — Gas chromatographic determination of volatile aromatic and halogenated hydrocarbons and selected ethers — Static headspace method
ISO 22892:2006	Soil quality — Guidelines for the identification of target compounds by gas chromatography and mass spectrometry
ISO 16558-1:2015	Soil quality — Risk-based petroleum hydrocarbons — Part 1: Determination of aliphatic and aromatic fractions of volatile petroleum hydrocarbons using gas chromatography (static headspace method)
ISO 16558-1:2015/Amd 1:2020	Soil quality — Risk-based petroleum hydrocarbons — Part 1: Determination of aliphatic and aromatic fractions of volatile petroleum hydrocarbons using gas chromatography (static headspace method) — Amendment 1
ISO 17183:2016	Soil quality — Screening soils for isopropanol-extractable organic compounds by determining emulsification index by light attenuation

Reference	Title
EN 17503:2022	Soil, sludge, treated biowaste and waste - Determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) by gas chromatography (GC) and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)
EN 16166:2021	Soil, treated biowaste and sludge - Determination of adsorbed organically bound halogens (AOX)
EN 16190:2018	Soil, treated biowaste and sludge - Determination of dioxins and furans and dioxin-like polychlorinated biphenyls by gas chromatography with high resolution mass selective detection (HR GC-MS)
ISO 13914:2023	Soil, treated biowaste and sludge — Determination of dioxins and furans and dioxin-like polychlorinated biphenyls by gas chromatography with high resolution mass selective detection (HR GC-MS)
EN 13656:2020	Soil, treated biowaste, sludge and waste - Digestion with a hydrochloric (HCl), nitric (HNO ₃) and tetrafluoroboric (HBF ₄) or hydrofluoric (HF) acid mixture for subsequent determination of elements

3.4.3. Pesticides and herbicides residues

Reference	Title
ISO 11264:2005	Soil quality — Determination of herbicides — Method using HPLC with UV-detection
ISO 10382:2002	Soil quality — Determination of organochlorine pesticides and polychlorinated biphenyls — Gas-chromatographic method with electron capture detection
ISO 23646:2022	Soil quality — Determination of organochlorine pesticides by gas chromatography with mass selective detection (GC-MS) and gas chromatography with electron-capture detection (GC-ECD)
ISO 20295:2018	Soil quality — Determination of perchlorate in soil using ion chromatography

Reference	Title
ISO 5120	Soil quality — Determination of perchlorate in soil using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)
ISO 14154:2005	Soil quality — Determination of some selected chlorophenols — Gas-chromatographic method with electron-capture detection
ISO/TS 17182:2014	Soil quality — Determination of some selected phenols and chlorophenols — Gas chromatographic method with mass spectrometric detection

3.4.4. Soil microbiology

Reference	Title
ISO 14238:2012	Soil quality — Biological methods — Determination of nitrogen mineralization and nitrification in soils and the influence of chemicals on these processes
ISO 18187:2016	Soil quality — Contact test for solid samples using the dehydrogenase activity of <i>Arthrobacter globiformis</i>
ISO 15685:2012	Soil quality — Determination of potential nitrification and inhibition of nitrification — Rapid test by ammonium oxidation
ISO 17155:2012	Soil quality — Determination of abundance and activity of soil microflora using respiration curves
ISO 23753-1:2019	Soil quality — Determination of dehydrogenases activity in soils — Part 1: Method using triphenyltetrazolium chloride (TTC)
ISO 23753-1:2019/Amd 1:2020	Soil quality — Determination of dehydrogenases activity in soils — Part 1: Method using triphenyltetrazolium chloride (TTC) — Amendment 1

Reference	Title
ISO 23753-2:2019	Soil quality — Determination of dehydrogenases activity in soils — Part 2: Method using iodotetrazolium chloride (INT)
ISO 23753-2:2019/Amd 1:2020	Soil quality — Determination of dehydrogenases activity in soils — Part 2: Method using iodotetrazolium chloride (INT) — Amendment 1
ISO 14240-1:1997	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial biomass — Part 1: Substrate-induced respiration method
ISO 14240-2:1997	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial biomass — Part 2: Fumigation-extraction method
ISO/TS 29843-1:2010	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial diversity — Part 1: Method by phospholipid fatty acid analysis (PLFA) and phospholipid ether lipids (PLEL) analysis
ISO/TS 29843-2:2021	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial diversity — Part 2: Method by phospholipid fatty acid analysis (PLFA) using the simple PLFA extraction method
ISO 11063:2020	Soil quality — Direct extraction of soil DNA
ISO/TS 20131-1:2018	Soil quality — Easy laboratory assessments of soil denitrification, a process source of N ₂ O emissions — Part 1: Soil denitrifying enzymes activities
ISO/TS 20131-2:2018	Soil quality — Easy laboratory assessments of soil denitrification, a process source of N ₂ O emissions — Part 2: Assessment of the capacity of soils to reduce N ₂ O
ISO/TS 10832:2009	Soil quality — Effects of pollutants on mycorrhizal fungi — Spore germination test
ISO 17601:2016	Soil quality — Estimation of abundance of selected microbial gene sequences by quantitative PCR from DNA directly extracted from soil
ISO 11266:1994	Soil quality — Guidance on laboratory testing for biodegradation of organic chemicals in soil under aerobic conditions

Reference	Title
ISO 15473:2002	Soil quality — Guidance on laboratory testing for biodegradation of organic chemicals in soil under anaerobic conditions
ISO 14239:2017	Soil quality — Laboratory incubation systems for measuring the mineralization of organic chemicals in soil under aerobic conditions
ISO 16072:2002	Soil quality — Laboratory methods for determination of microbial soil respiration
ISO 20130:2018	Soil quality — Measurement of enzyme activity patterns in soil samples using colorimetric substrates in micro-well plates
ISO/TS 22939:2019	Soil quality — Measurement of enzyme activity patterns in soil samples using fluorogenic substrates in micro-well plates
ISO 18400-206:2018	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 206: Collection, handling and storage of soil under aerobic conditions for the assessment of microbiological processes, biomass and diversity in the laboratory
ISO 23265:2022	Soil quality — Test for estimating organic matter decomposition in contaminated soil

3.4.5. Soil fauna

Reference	Title
ISO 17512-1:2008	Soil quality — Avoidance test for determining the quality of soils and effects of chemicals on behaviour — Part 1: Test with earthworms (<i>Eisenia fetida</i> and <i>Eisenia andrei</i>)
ISO 17512-2:2011	Soil quality — Avoidance test for determining the quality of soils and effects of chemicals on behaviour — Part 2: Test with collembolans (<i>Folsomia candida</i>)

Reference	Title
ISO 16387:2023	Soil quality — Effects of contaminants on <i>Enchytraeidae</i> <i>Enchytraeus</i> sp. — Determination of effects on reproduction
ISO 11268-1:2012	Soil quality — Effects of pollutants on earthworms — Part 1: Determination of acute toxicity to <i>Eisenia fetida</i> / <i>Eisenia andrei</i>
ISO 11268-2:2023	Soil quality — Effects of pollutants on earthworms — Part 2: Determination of effects on reproduction of <i>Eisenia fetida</i> / <i>Eisenia andrei</i> and other earthworm species
ISO 11268-3:2014	Soil quality — Effects of pollutants on earthworms — Part 3: Guidance on the determination of effects in field situations
ISO 20963:2005	Soil quality — Effects of pollutants on insect larvae (<i>Oxythyrea funesta</i>) — Determination of acute toxicity
ISO 15952:2018	Soil quality — Effects of pollutants on juvenile land snails (<i>Helicidae</i>) — Determination of the effects on growth by soil contamination
ISO 21286:2019	Soil quality — Identification of ecotoxicological test species by DNA barcoding
ISO 24032:2021	Soil quality — In situ caging of snails to assess bioaccumulation of contaminants
ISO 11267:2014	Soil quality — Inhibition of reproduction of <i>Collembola</i> (<i>Folsomia candida</i>) by soil contaminants
ISO 21285:2019	Soil quality — Inhibition of reproduction of the soil mite (<i>Hypoaspis aculeifer</i>) by soil contaminants
ISO 18311:2016	Soil quality — Method for testing effects of soil contaminants on the feeding activity of soil dwelling organisms — Bait-lamina test
ISO 23611-1:2018	Soil quality — Sampling of soil invertebrates — Part 1: Hand-sorting and extraction of earthworms

Reference	Title
ISO 23611-2:2006	Soil quality — Sampling of soil invertebrates — Part 2: Sampling and extraction of micro-arthropods (Collembola and Acarina)
ISO 23611-3:2019	Soil quality — Sampling of soil invertebrates — Part 3: Sampling and extraction of enchytraeids
ISO 23611-4:2022	Soil quality — Sampling of soil invertebrates — Part 4: Sampling, extraction and identification of soil-inhabiting nematodes
ISO 23611-5:2011	Soil quality — Sampling of soil invertebrates — Part 5: Sampling and extraction of soil macro-invertebrates
ISO 23611-6:2012	Soil quality — Sampling of soil invertebrates — Part 6: Guidance for the design of sampling programmes with soil invertebrates
ISO 23265:2022	Soil quality — Test for estimating organic matter decomposition in contaminated soil
ISO 23266:2020	Soil quality — Test for measuring the inhibition of reproduction in oribatid mites <i>Oppia nitens</i> exposed to contaminants in soil
EN ISO 10872:2021	Water and soil quality - Determination of the toxic effect of sediment and soil samples on growth, fertility and reproduction of <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> (Nematoda) (ISO 10872:2020)

3.4.6. Soil flora

Reference	Title
ISO 11269-1:2012	Soil quality — Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora — Part 1: Method for the measurement of inhibition of root growth
ISO 11269-2:2012	Soil quality — Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora — Part 2: Effects of contaminated soil on the emergence and early growth of higher plants
ISO 17126:2005	Soil quality — Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora — Screening test for emergence of lettuce seedlings (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.)
ISO 18763:2016	Soil quality — Determination of the toxic effects of pollutants on germination and early growth of higher plants
ISO 21479:2019	Soil quality — Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora — Leaf fatty acid composition of plants used to assess soil quality
ISO 22030:2005	Soil quality — Biological methods — Chronic toxicity in higher plants
ISO 29200:2013	Soil quality — Assessment of genotoxic effects on higher plants — <i>Vicia faba</i> micronucleus test

3.4.7. Soil remediation

Reference	Title
ISO 15176:2019	Guidance on characterization of excavated soil and other materials intended for re-use
ISO 17924:2018	Soil quality — Assessment of human exposure from ingestion of soil and soil material — Procedure for the estimation of the human bioaccessibility/bioavailability of metals in soil
ISO 15175:2018	Soil quality — Characterization of contaminated soil related to groundwater protection
ISO 15800:2019	Soil quality — Characterization of soil with respect to human exposure
ISO 21365:2019	Soil quality — Conceptual site models for potentially contaminated sites
ISO 21365:2019	Soil quality — Conceptual site models for potentially contaminated sites
ISO 16751:2020	Soil quality — Environmental availability of non-polar organic compounds — Determination of the potentially bioavailable fraction and the non-bioavailable fraction using a strong adsorbent or complexing agent
ISO 18772:2008	Soil quality — Guidance on leaching procedures for subsequent chemical and ecotoxicological testing of soils and soil materials
ISO 17616:2019	Soil quality — Guidance on the choice and evaluation of bioassays for ecotoxicological characterization of soils and soil materials
ISO 19258:2018	Soil quality — Guidance on the determination of background values
ISO 15799:2019	Soil quality — Guidance on the ecotoxicological characterization of soils and soil materials

Reference	Title
ISO 21268-1:2019	Soil quality — Leaching procedures for subsequent chemical and ecotoxicological testing of soil and soil-like materials — Part 1: Batch test using a liquid to solid ratio of 2 l/kg dry matter
ISO 21268-2:2019	Soil quality — Leaching procedures for subsequent chemical and ecotoxicological testing of soil and soil-like materials — Part 2: Batch test using a liquid to solid ratio of 10 l/kg dry matter
ISO 21268-3:2019	Soil quality — Leaching procedures for subsequent chemical and ecotoxicological testing of soil and soil-like materials — Part 3: Up-flow percolation test
ISO 21268-4:2019	Soil quality — Leaching procedures for subsequent chemical and ecotoxicological testing of soil and soil-like materials — Part 4: Influence of pH on leaching with initial acid/base addition
ISO 16198:2015	Soil quality — Plant-based test to assess the environmental bioavailability of trace elements to plants
ISO 19204:2017	Soil quality — Procedure for site-specific ecological risk assessment of soil contamination (soil quality TRIAD approach)
ISO 17402:2008	Soil quality — Requirements and guidance for the selection and application of methods for the assessment of bioavailability of contaminants in soil and soil materials
ISO 18504:2017	Soil quality — Sustainable remediation
ISO 22190:2020	Soil quality — Use of extracts for the assessment of bioavailability of trace elements in soils

3.4.8. Data management

Reference	Title
ISO 15903:2002	Soil quality — Format for recording soil and site information
ISO 23992:2022	Soil quality — Framework for detailed recording and monitoring of changes in dynamic soil properties
ISO 25177:2019	Soil quality — Field soil description
ISO 28258:2013	Soil quality — Digital exchange of soil-related data
ISO 28258:2013/Amd 1:2019	Soil quality — Digital exchange of soil-related data — Amendment 1

3.4.9. Climate change

Reference	Title
ISO 20951:2019	Soil Quality — Guidance on methods for measuring greenhouse gases (CO ₂ , N ₂ O, CH ₄) and ammonia (NH ₃) fluxes between soils and the atmosphere
ISO 23400:2021	Guidelines for the determination of organic carbon and nitrogen stocks and their variations in mineral soils at field scale
ISO 4974	Soil quality — Guidance on soil temperature measurement

3.5. Standards related to plastics and microplastics.

The international committee

European standards on plastics are being developed by **CEN/TC 249 “Plastics”**, where the standardization of methods and specifications plastics, plastic-based materials, semi-finished products and products is developed.

The international committee **ISO/TC 61/SC 14 “Plastics. Environmental aspects”**, covers standardization activities in the field of plastics relating to environmental and sustainability aspects. The focus is on, but not limited to biobased plastics, biodegradability, environmental footprint incl. carbon footprint, resource efficiency incl. circular economy, characterization of plastics leaked into the environment incl. microplastics, waste management incl. organic, mechanical and chemical recycling.

Reference	Title
ISO 17556:2019	Plastics — Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials in soil by measuring the oxygen demand in a respirometer or the amount of carbon dioxide evolved
ISO/TR 21960:2020	Plastics — Environmental aspects — State of knowledge and methodologies

3.6. Standards related to geographic information.

The international committee **ISO/TC 211 “Geographic information/Geomatics”**, is responsible of the standardization in the field of geographic information. This work aims to establish a structured set of standards for information concerning objects or phenomena that are directly or indirectly associated with a location relative to the Earth.

Within the scope of geographic information, these standards may specify methods, tools, and services for data management. Data management is understood to include acquiring, processing, analyzing, accessing, presenting, and publishing data for users and systems.

The work shall link to appropriate standards for information technology and data where possible, and provide a framework for the development of sector-specific applications using geographic data.

Reference	Title
ISO/TS 19115-3:2016	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 3: XML schema implementation for fundamental concepts
ISO 19144-1:2009	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 1: Classification system structure
ISO 19144-1:2009/Cor 1:2012	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 1: Classification system structure — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 19144-2:2012	Geographic information - Classification systems — Part 2: Land Cover Meta Language (LCML)
ISO 19137:2007	Geographic information — Core profile of the spatial schema
ISO 19126:2021	Geographic information — Feature concept dictionaries and registers
ISO 19152:2012	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM)
ISO 19115-1:2014	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19115-1:2014/Amd 1:2018	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals — Amendment 1
ISO 19115-1:2014/Amd 2:2020	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals — Amendment 2
ISO 19115-3	Geographic information — Metadata — Part 3: XML schema implementation for fundamental concepts
ISO 19110:2016	Geographic information — Methodology for feature cataloguing
ISO 19165-1:2018	Geographic information — Preservation of digital data and metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals
ISO 19165-2:2020	Geographic information — Preservation of digital data and metadata — Part 2: Content specifications for Earth observation data and derived digital products

Reference	Title
ISO 19145:2013	Geographic information — Registry of representations of geographic point location
ISO/TS 19139-1:2019	Geographic information — XML schema implementation — Part 1: Encoding rules

3.7. Standards related to oil quality.

The international committee **ISO/TC 34/SC 11 “Animal and vegetable fats and oils”**, is responsible of the standardization of methods of sampling and analysis of animal, marine and vegetable fats and oils but excluding methods of analysis developed specifically for milk and milk products.

Also, as previously indicated, IOC develops standardized documents that covers olive oil quality field.

Reference	Title
COI/T.20/Doc. No 15	Sensory analysis of olive oil – method for the organoleptic assessment of virgin olive oil
ISO 15303:2001	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Detection and identification of a volatile organic contaminant by GC/MS
ISO 5558:1982	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Detection and identification of antioxidants — Thin-layer chromatographic method
ISO 7366:1987	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of 1-monoglycerides and free glycerol contents
ISO 660:2020	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of acid value and acidity
ISO 10539:2002	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of alkalinity
ISO 6885:2016	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of anisidine value
ISO 6884:2008	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of ash

Reference	Title
ISO 18301:2014	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of conventional mass per volume (litre weight in air) — Oscillating U-tube method
ISO 6883:2017	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of conventional mass per volume (litre weight in air)
ISO 663:2017	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of insoluble impurities content
ISO 3961:2018	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of iodine value
ISO 13884:2003	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of isolated trans isomers by infrared spectrometry
ISO 15305:1998	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of Lovibond colour
ISO 27608:2010	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of Lovibond® colour — Automatic method
ISO 27608:2010/Amd 1:2016	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of Lovibond® colour — Automatic method — Amendment 1
ISO 6321:2021	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of melting point in open capillary tubes — Slip point
ISO 662:2016	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of moisture and volatile matter content
ISO 6886:2016	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of oxidative stability (accelerated oxidation test)
ISO 27107:2008	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of peroxide value — Potentiometric end-point determination
ISO 3960:2017	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of peroxide value — Iodometric (visual) endpoint determination
ISO 6320:2017	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of refractive index

Reference	Title
ISO 3657:2020	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of saponification value
ISO 15301:2001	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of sediment in crude fats and oils — Centrifuge method
ISO 15301:2001/Cor 1:2007	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of sediment in crude fats and oils — Centrifuge method — Technical Corrigendum 1
ISO 8292-1:2008	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of solid fat content by pulsed NMR — Part 1: Direct method
ISO 8292-2:2008	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of solid fat content by pulsed NMR — Part 2: Indirect method
ISO 6800:1997	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of the composition of fatty acids in the 2-position of the triglyceride molecules
ISO 935:1988	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of titre
ISO 9936:2016	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of tocopherol and tocotrienol contents by high-performance liquid chromatography
ISO 3656:2011	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of ultraviolet absorbance expressed as specific UV extinction
ISO 3656:2011/Amd 1:2017	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of ultraviolet absorbance expressed as specific UV extinction — Amendment 1
ISO 18609:2000	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of unsaponifiable matter — Method using hexane extraction
ISO 3596:2000	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of unsaponifiable matter — Method using diethyl ether extraction
ISO 19219:2002	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of visible foots in crude fats and oils

Reference	Title
ISO 8534:2017	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of water content — Karl Fischer method (pyridine free)
ISO 934:1980	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of water content — Entrainment method
ISO 15267:1998	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Flashpoint limit test using Pensky-Martens closed cup flash tester
ISO 661:2003	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Preparation of test sample
ISO 5555:2001	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Sampling
ISO 5555:2001/Amd 1:2014	Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Sampling — Amendment 1: Flexitanks
ISO 24363:2023	Determination of fatty acid methyl esters (<i>cis</i> and <i>trans</i>) and squalene in olive oil and other vegetable oils by gas chromatography
ISO 12871:2019	Olive oils and olive-pomace oils — Determination of aliphatic and triterpenic alcohols content by capillary gas chromatography
ISO 12872:2022	Olive oils and olive-pomace oils — Determination of the 2-glycerol monopalmitate content
ISO 12873:2010	Olive oils and olive-pomace oils — Determination of wax content by capillary gas chromatography

3.8. Standards related to environmental management.

The international committee **ISO/TC 207“Environmental management ”**, is responsible of the standardization in the field of environmental management to address environmental and climate impacts, including related social and economic aspects, in support of sustainable development.

Reference	Title
ISO 14055-1:2017	Environmental management — Guidelines for establishing good practices for combatting land degradation and desertification — Part 1: Good practices framework
ISO/TR 14055-2:2022	Environmental management — Guidelines for establishing good practices for combatting land degradation and desertification — Part 2: Regional case studies
ISO/TR 14047:2012	Environmental management -- Life cycle assessment -- Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14044 to impact assessment situations
ISO 14040:2006	Environmental management -- Life cycle assessment -- Principles and framework
ISO 14040:2006/Amd 1:2020	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework — Amendment 1
ISO 14044:2006	Environmental management -- Life cycle assessment -- Requirements and guidelines
ISO 14044:2006+ Amd 1:2017	Environmental management -- Life cycle assessment -- Requirements and guidelines — Amendment 1
ISO 14044:2006+ Amd 1:2020	Environmental management -- Life cycle assessment -- Requirements and guidelines — Amendment 2

3.9. Standards under development

The following standards are related to the areas listed previously , but its development is on-going

Reference	Title
ISO/AWI 18721	Assessment of ecological soil functions: indicators and methods
ISO/AWI 18718	Assessment of soil functions and related-ecosystem services: definitions and conceptual Framework
ISO/PWI 11964	Effects of structure formation on soil – chemical and physical properties
ISO/PWI 21744	Environmental matrices - Soil, sediment, solid and liquid waste, treated biowaste and sludge - Guidance for sample pretreatment
ISO/CD 18227	Environmental solid matrices — Determination of elemental composition by X-ray fluorescence
ISO/FDIS 22036	Environmental solid matrices — Determination of elements using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES)
ISO/DIS 18475	Environmental solid matrices — Determination of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB) by gas chromatography — Mass selective detection (GC-MS) or electron-capture detection (GC-ECD)
ISO/CD 11265	Environmental solid matrices — Determination of the specific electrical conductivity
ISO/CD 16965	Environmental solid matrices — Determination of trace elements using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)
ISO/DIS 19144-2	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 2: Land Cover Meta Language (LCML)
ISO/AWI TS 19144-3	Geographic information — Classification systems — Part 3: Land Use Meta Language (LUML)

Reference	Title
ISO/CD 19152-2	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 2: Land registration
ISO/CD 19152-4	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 4: Valuation information
ISO/CD 19152-5	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 5: Spatial plan information
ISO/DIS 19152-1	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 1: Generic Conceptual Model
ISO/PWI 19152-6	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 6: Part 6: Implementation aspects
ISO/FDIS 24187	Principles for the analysis of microplastics present in the environment
ISO/DIS 24212	Remediation techniques applied at contaminated sites
ISO/CD 7303	Simplified method for oral bioaccessibility of metal(loid)s in soils
ISO/NP 19254	Simultaneous determination of multi-class pesticide residues in soil using GC-MS/MS and LC-MS/MS analysis
ISO/CD 15192	Soil and waste — Determination of Chromium(VI) in solid material by alkaline digestion and ion chromatography with spectrometric detection
FprEN 17505	Soil and waste characterization - Temperature dependent differentiation of total carbon (TOC400, ROC, TIC900)
ISO/DIS 8259	Soil quality — Bioaccessibility of organic and inorganic pollutants from contaminated soil and soil-like material
ISO/DIS 18187	Soil quality — Contact test for solid samples using the dehydrogenase activity of <i>Arthrobacter globiformis</i>

Reference	Title
ISO 11277:2020/DAMd 1	Soil quality — Determination of particle size distribution in mineral soil material — Method by sieving and sedimentation — Amendment 1
ISO/DIS 22171	Soil quality — Determination of potential cation exchange capacity (CEC) and exchangeable cations buffered at pH 7, using a molar ammonium acetate solution
ISO/DIS 17126	Soil quality — Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora — Screening test for emergence of lettuce seedlings (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.)
ISO/FDIS 11267	Soil quality — Inhibition of reproduction of <i>Collembola Folsomia candida</i> by soil contaminants
ISO/DIS 21268-5	Soil quality — Leaching procedures for subsequent chemical and ecotoxicological testing of soil and soil-like materials — Part 5: Batch test with forced aerobic or anaerobic conditions
ISO/AWI 19204	Soil quality — Procedure for site-specific ecological risk assessment of soil contamination (soil quality TRIAD approach)
ISO/AWI 18400-105	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 105: Packaging, transport, storage and preservation of samples
ISO/FDIS 18400-301	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 301: Sampling and on site semi-quantitative determinations of volatile organic compounds in field investigations
ISO/FDIS 18400-301	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 301: Sampling and on site semi-quantitative determinations of volatile organic compounds in field investigations
ISO/DIS 23611-2	Soil quality — Sampling of soil invertebrates — Part 2: Sampling and extraction of micro-arthropods (<i>Collembola</i> and <i>Acarina</i>)
ISO/DIS 23611-5	Soil quality — Sampling of soil invertebrates — Part 5: Sampling and extraction of soil macro-invertebrates
ISO/CD 18386	Soil quality — Screening method for soil temperature — Measurement by IR thermometer

Reference	Title
ISO/CD 13196	Soil quality — Screening soils for selected elements by energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometry using a handheld or portable instrument

4. Conclusions

As a result of the study of the standardization landscape through the methodology explained above, several standards relevant for the SOIL O-LIVE project have been found.

18 standards have been identified as relevant for the project they refer to WP2, WP3, WP4, WP 5 and WP6.

In the future it might be possible to contribute to those standards through standards usage information and through the dissemination of the SOIL O-LIVE framework which may include those standards. There will also be possible to report failures, improvement or any other kinds of suggestions.

Private standardization initiatives (International Olive Council) have also been identified as relevant for the project. Information about them is publicly available. It might be possible to contribute in the future to communities developing those initiatives sharing with them part of the developments from SOIL O-LIVE.

To be able to use the standardization system as a tool for dissemination of the project results an interaction with the market stakeholders will be necessary. It will be necessary to decide the interaction that SOIL O-LIVE's will have with the standardization technical committees relevant for SOIL O-LIVE (see Table 3). UNE will provide with the necessary technical support required for that interaction.

5. References

- [1]. CEN website (<https://www.cencenelec.eu/about-cen/>)
- [2]. ISO website (<https://www.iso.org/>)
- [3]. IOC website (<https://www.internationaloliveoil.org/>)

6. Acronyms

CEN	European Committee for Standardization
EN	European Standard
ISO	International Organization for Standardization; International Standard
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
VA	Vienna Agreement
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardization
WG	Working Group

ANNEX I. Scope of the relevant standards identified

Reference	Title	Scope
ISO 18400-205:2018	Soil quality. Sampling . Part 205: Guidance on the procedure for investigation of natural, near-natural and cultivated sites	<p><i>This document provides guidance on the sampling of soils of</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>natural and near-natural sites,</i> ▪ <i>natural arboreal areas including forests and woods,</i> ▪ <i>areas used for agriculture (arable and pasture sites),</i> ▪ <i>areas used for horticulture (including domestic gardens, allotments), and</i> ▪ <i>areas used for special crop-cultivation, orchards, vineyards, commercial plantations and forests, etc.</i> <p><i>It is applicable to soil investigations and evaluations in the field, and collection of samples for chemical, geochemical, physical, and biological characterization of soil and soil materials in the laboratory.</i></p> <p><i>This document sets out appropriate strategies for the design of sampling programmes, field procedures and subsequent treatment of samples for transport and storage prior to sample pretreatment (e.g. drying, milling). It is intended to be used in conjunction with the other parts of the ISO 18400 series. Attention is, in particular, drawn to the requirements concerning collection, handling and storage of soil for assessment of biological functions in ISO 18400-206.</i></p> <p><i>NOTE 1 Groundwater and surface water can be adversely impacted by agricultural and related activities, such as nitrates and pesticides, and by translocation of soil particles. In turn, knowledge about water quality can provide information about possible sources of groundwater contamination or contaminating run-off. Investigation of groundwater and surface water quality is outside of the scope of this document; relevant guidance is given in the ISO 5667 series of standards. ISO 15175 provides guidance on the relationship between soil properties and groundwater quality.</i></p> <p><i>NOTE 2 It could also be appropriate to investigate ambient air, vegetation, potable water supplies and a variety of other media depending on the findings of the preliminary investigation.</i></p>

Reference	Title	Scope
ISO 11264:2005	Soil quality — Determination of herbicides — Method using HPLC with UV-detection	<i>ISO 11264:2005 specifies a high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method for qualitative and quantitative determination of herbicides of various substance classes in soils. This method covers triazines including their related metabolites, phenyl urea compounds and other herbicides. Compounds are identified and quantified with UV-detection</i>
ISO 10382:2002	Soil quality — Determination of organochlorine pesticides and polychlorinated biphenyls — Gas-chromatographic method with electron capture detection	<i>ISO 10382:2002 specifies a method for quantitative determination of seven polychlorinated biphenyls and seventeen organochlorine pesticides in soil.</i> <i>ISO 10382:2002 is applicable to all types of soil.</i> <i>Under the conditions specified in ISO 10382:2002, limits of detection of 0,1 micrograms per kilogram to 4 micrograms per kilogram (expressed as dry matter) can be achieved</i>
ISO 11063:2020	Soil quality — Direct extraction of soil DNA	<i>The present document specifies a method for direct extraction of DNA from soil samples to analyse the abundance and composition of microbial communities by various techniques of molecular biology including real-time quantitative PCR (qPCR). This method is mainly dedicated to agricultural and forest soils. This method can possibly not be suitable for soils rich in organic matter (e.g. peat soils) or soils heavily polluted with organic pollutants or heavy metals.</i> <i>The direct extraction of DNA from soil samples provides unique insight into the α- and β-diversity of microbial communities. Next-generation sequencing of amplicons obtained by PCR (polymerase chain reaction) amplification of soil DNA constitutes a promising domain which will in the near future contribute to the development of routine tools to monitor microbial communities in soil environments</i>

Reference	Title	Scope
ISO 14240-1:1997	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial biomass — Part 1: Substrate-induced respiration method	<i>Contains a method for the determination of the active aerobic, heterotrophic microbial biomass in aerated agricultural and mineral soil</i>
ISO 14240-2:1997	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial biomass — Part 2: Fumigation-extraction method	<i>Gives a method for the determination of microbial biomass of soils by measurement of total extractable organic biomass material mainly from freshly killed microorganisms. It is also applicable to the estimation of microbial nitrogen and ninhydrin-reactive nitrogen in soil.</i>
ISO/TS 10832:2009	Soil quality — Effects of pollutants on mycorrhizal fungi — Spore germination test	<i>ISO/TS 10832:2009 specifies a method to evaluate the effects of pollutants on spore germination of a mycorrhizal fungus, <i>Glomus mosseae</i>. This direct acute toxicity bioassay allows the evaluation of potential effects of pollutants and contaminated soils on beneficial soil microorganisms important for plant growth within the concept of sustainable agriculture.</i> <i>ISO/TS 10832:2009 is applicable to chemical substances, and contaminated soils, waste and soil-waste mixture and sludge.</i>
ISO 21286:2019	Soil quality — Identification of ecotoxicological test species by DNA barcoding	<i>This document specifies a protocol to identify ecotoxicological test specimens (mainly invertebrates and plants) to the species level, based on the DNA barcoding technique. This protocol can be used by laboratories performing DNA barcoding in order to standardize both the wet-lab and data analysis workflows as much as possible, and make them compliant with community standards and guidelines.</i> <i>This document does not intend to specify one particular strain for each test method, but to accurately document the species/strain which was used.</i>

Reference	Title	Scope
		<p><i>NOTE 1 This does not imply that DNA barcoding is performed in parallel to each test run, but rather regularly (e.g. once a year, such as reference substance testing) and each time a new culture is started or new individuals are added to an ongoing culture.</i></p> <p><i>This document does not aim at duplicating or replacing morphological-based species identifications. On the contrary, DNA barcoding is proposed as a complementary identification tool where morphology is inconclusive, or to diagnose cryptic species, in order to ensure that the results obtained from different ecotoxicological laboratories are referring to the same species or strain.</i></p> <p><i>This document is applicable to identifications of immature forms which lack morphological diagnostic characters (eggs, larvae, juveniles), as well as the streamline identification of specimens collected in field monitoring studies, where large numbers of organisms from diverse taxa are classified.</i></p> <p><i>NOTE 2 In principle, all species regularly used in ecotoxicological testing can be analysed by DNA barcoding. Besides the earthworms Eisenia fetida and E. andrei, further examples for terrestrial species are Lumbricus terrestris, L. rubellus, Allolobophora chlorotica, Aporectodea rosea, and A. caliginosa, Dendrodrilus rubidus, Enchytraeus albidus, and E. crypticus (Haplotaenida); Folsomia candida, F. fimetaria, Proisotoma minuta, and Sinella curviseta (Collembola); Hypoaspis aculeifer and Oppia nitens (Acari); Aleochara bilineata and Poecilus cupreus (Coleoptera); Scathophaga stercoraria, Musca autumnalis (Diptera) or Pardosa sp. (Arachnida). Nematodes or snails and even plants can also be added to this list</i></p>
ISO 18504:2017	Soil quality — Sustainable remediation	<p><i>ISO 18504:2017 provides procedures on sustainable remediation. In particular, it provides:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>- standard methodology, terminology and information about the key components and aspects of sustainable remediation assessment;</i> <i>- informative advice on the assessment of the relative sustainability of alternative remediation strategies.</i> <p><i>ISO 18504:2017 is intended to inform practitioners about contemporary understanding of sustainable remediation. It is not intended to prescribe which methods of assessment, indicators or weights to use.</i></p>

Reference	Title	Scope
		<p><i>Rather, it is intended to inform consideration of the concept of sustainable remediation in a local legal, policy, socio-economic and environmental context.</i></p> <p><i>The scope of ISO 18504:2017 is restricted to sustainable remediation that is demonstrably breaking the source-pathway-receptor linkages ? in a manner that has been shown on a site-specific basis under a specific legal context to be sustainable.</i></p> <p><i>The concepts of "green remediation" and "green and sustainable remediation" (so called GSR) that in some parts of the world are conflated with sustainable remediation are neither endorsed nor discussed in ISO 18504:2017.</i></p>
ISO 19152:2012	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM)	<p><i>ISO 19152:2012:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>defines a reference Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) covering basic information-related components of land administration (including those over water and land, and elements above and below the surface of the earth);</i> - <i>provides an abstract, conceptual model with four packages related to parties (people and organizations); basic administrative units, rights, responsibilities, and restrictions (ownership rights); spatial units (parcels, and the legal space of buildings and utility networks); spatial sources (surveying), and spatial representations (geometry and topology);</i> - <i>provides terminology for land administration, based on various national and international systems, that is as simple as possible in order to be useful in practice. The terminology allows a shared description of different formal or informal practices and procedures in various jurisdictions;</i> - <i>provides a basis for national and regional profiles; and</i> - <i>enables the combining of land administration information from different sources in a coherent manner.</i>
ISO 24363:2023	Determination of fatty acid methyl esters	<p><i>This document specifies the determination of the fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) and squalene in olive oil and other vegetable oils by gas chromatography (GC).</i></p>

Reference	Title	Scope
	(<i>cis</i>) and (<i>trans</i>) and squalene in olive oil and other vegetable oils by gas chromatography	<i>This document is applicable to the determination of FAME from C12 to C24, including saturated, cis- and trans-monounsaturated, cis- and trans-polyunsaturated FAME and squalene</i>
ISO 12871:2019	Olive oils and olive-pomace oils — Determination of aliphatic and triterpenic alcohols content by capillary gas chromatography	<i>This document specifies a procedure for the determination of the content, as a mass fraction expressed as milligrams per kilogram, of aliphatic and triterpenic alcohols in olive oils and olive-pomace oils.</i> <i>NOTE This document is based on COI/T.20/Doc. 26 Rev.2:2017</i>
ISO 12872:2022	Olive oils and olive-pomace oils — Determination of the 2-glycerol monopalmitate content	<i>This document specifies a procedure for the determination of the content, as a percentage mass fraction, of 2-glycerol monopalmitate in olive oils and olive-pomace oils that are liquid at ambient temperature (20 °C).</i> <i>NOTE This document is based on COI/T.20/Doc. No 23/Rev.1:2017[7].</i>
ISO 12873:2010	Olive oils and olive-pomace oils — Determination of wax content by capillary gas chromatography	<i>ISO 12873:2010 specifies the determination of the wax content, as a mass fraction expressed in milligrams per kilogram, of olive oils and olive-pomace oils. The individual waxes are separated according to the number of carbon atoms. The method is recommended for distinguishing between olive oil obtained by pressing or centrifuging and that obtained from olive pomace (olive-pomace oil).</i>

Reference	Title	Scope
COI/T.20/Doc. No 15	Sensory analysis of olive oil – method for the organoleptic assessment of virgin olive oil	<p><i>The purpose of this international method is to determine the procedure for assessing the organoleptic characteristics of virgin olive oil and to establish the method for its classification on the basis of those characteristics.</i></p> <p><i>The method described is only applicable to virgin olive oils and to the classification of such oils according to the intensity of the defects perceived and of the fruitiness, as determined by a group of tasters selected, trained and monitored as a panel.</i></p> <p><i>It also provides indications for optional labelling</i></p>
ISO 14055-1:2017	Environmental management — Guidelines for establishing good practices for combatting land degradation and desertification — Part 1: Good practices framework	<p><i>ISO 14055-1:2017 provides guidelines for establishing good practices in land management to prevent or minimize land degradation and desertification. It does not include management of coastal wetlands.</i></p> <p><i>ISO 14055-1:2017 defines a framework for identifying good practices in land management, based on assessment of the drivers of land degradation and risks associated with current and past practices. Guidance on monitoring and reporting implementation of good practices is also provided.</i></p> <p><i>ISO 14055-1:2017 is intended for use by private and public sector organizations with responsibility for land management and will allow an organization to communicate implementation of good practices.</i></p>
ISO/TR 14055-2:2022	Environmental management — Guidelines for establishing good practices for combatting land degradation and desertification — Part 2: Regional case studies	<p><i>This document provides regional case studies of good practices in land management to prevent or minimize land degradation and desertification in support of ISO 14055-1:2017.</i></p> <p><i>The case studies are presented to facilitate the application of ISO 14055-1 across a wide of range of geographical and local conditions.</i></p> <p><i>NOTE The cases studies are presented as different ways of applying good practice and do not preclude alternative ways of applying good practices in accordance with ISO 14055-1.</i></p>

<p>ISO/AWI 18721</p>	<p>Assessment of ecological soil functions: indicators and methods</p>	<p><i>This standard provides generic guidance on how core Ecological Soil Functions (ESF) can be evaluated in different contexts of land use and management (e.g. agricultural, forest or contaminated lands) for environmental monitoring. Ecological soil functions can be assessed the same way no matter which soil use is being considered. For each ESF, the standard specifically proposes biotic and abiotic parameters to be measured and associated indicators. It focuses on parameters and indicators that are either available as ISO standards or published in peer reviewed papers. This document does not apply to non-ecological soil functions such as geotechnical functions (foundation support for buildings, tunnels, etc.) or geothermal functions. Methods based on proxy indicators (e.g. soil occupation, hydrography parameters) are not included in this standard.</i></p>
----------------------	--	--

Reference	Title	Scope
ISO/NP 19254	Simultaneous determination of multi-class pesticide residues in soil using GC-MS/MS and LC-MS/MS analysis	--
ISO/FDIS 24187	Principles for the analysis of microplastics present in the environment	<p><i>This document describes the principles to be followed in the analysis of plastics in various environmental matrices (plastics testing). This includes the unique particle size classification of plastics, the use of certain apparatus with regard to sampling, sample preparation, and the determination of representative sample quantities. The purpose of this standard is to specify minimum requirements until specific standards for the different case situations are available. This is important to ensure that the development of the specific standards is done on a consistent basis to ensure that comparison or correlation of results is possible.</i></p> <p><i>This standard does not include requirements for monitoring actions.</i></p>

Reference	Title	Scope
ISO/CD 19152-2	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 2: Land registration	<p><i>Scope of the proposed deliverable This part of ISO 19152 provides the concepts and detailed structure for standardization in the land administration domain. In order to achieve public policy objectives, some regulations use geographical spaces for mandating or enabling particular behaviours or outcomes. International law, constitutional law, public law and private law define different geographical spaces that juxtapose or overlap each other to produce a complex legal reality. Harmonizing and integrating the activities related to management of these legal spaces is the overarching idea of the land administration paradigm. Even if they differ in their objectives and normative sources, objects created by geo-regulation share basic components. This part of ISO 19152 defines a general schema that permits regulatory information to be described in information systems. Essentially, legal actors – individuals, organizations, States – (party) create among themselves sets of obligations (rights, restrictions, responsibilities) with the specificity of having a geographical component (spatial unit). The way the legal spaces related to reality is defined by the survey system (survey and representation). All these elements are recognized through legal instruments and official documents (source). The first edition of this standard, ISO 19152:2012 concentrated on Land Administration, Land Registration and Cadastre. This information is about the relationship between people and land. This is now included in Part 2 with a more refined survey model. This part of the standard provides an abstract, conceptual model with three packages and one sub-package related to</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• parties (people and organizations);</i> <i>• basic administrative units, rights, responsibilities, and restrictions (ownership rights) -2];</i> <i>• spatial units (parcels, and the legal space of buildings and utility networks and other geometry) with a sub-package on surveying and spatial representation (geometry and topology).</i>

Reference	Title	Scope
ISO/CD 19152-4	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 4: Valuation information	<i>This part of ISO 19152 provides the concepts and detailed structure for standardization in the land administration domain. In order to achieve public policy objectives, some regulations use geographical spaces for mandating or enabling particular behaviours or outcomes. This part of ISO 19152 defines a general schema for valuation information systems in the context of the land administration. It is designed to represent all stages of administrative property valuation, namely representation of parties involved in valuations, identification of properties, assessment of properties through single or mass appraisal procedures, recording transaction prices, generation and representation of sales statistics, and dealing with appeals. The proposed model in this standard may provide public bodies a common basis for the development of local and/or national information models and databases, enabling the integration of valuation databases with land administration databases, and can act as a guide for the private sector The first edition of LADM standard, ISO 19152:2012 concentrated on Land Administration and value component of land administration was considered in out of scope. This information is now included in Part 4 with a more general perspective. This part of the standard provides an abstract, conceptual model related to • value (valuation, mass valuation); • transaction prices; • sales statistics; • valuation units (parcel, building, condominium unit, valuation unit group)</i>
ISO/CD 19152-5	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 5: Spatial plan information	<i>ISO 19152 provides the concepts and detailed structure for standardization in the land administration domain. In order to achieve public policy objectives, some regulations use geographical spaces for mandating or enabling particular behaviours or outcomes. This part of ISO 19152 defines a general schema for spatial plan information in the context of the land administration. This standard proposes integrating the Rights, Restrictions, and Responsibilities (RRRs) information from the spatial plan information, as an additional package, into the ISO 19152:2012 – Geographic Information – Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) standard. It provides the general reference model, as an extension of core LADM (ISO 19152-1:202X and 19152-2:202X), for all objects of spatial planning those covering land/water and below/on/above surfaces. This standard supports 4D (3D + time) representation of the spatial plans including marine spatial plans. Spatial plan information plays an essential role in land management. The integration of physical and sectoral planning at the local level usually produces some degree of permissions, authorizations, restrictions, responsibilities,</i>

Reference	Title	Scope
		<p><i>obligations, and sanctions. However, it is typical in many countries to establish land administration and the spatial plan processes through different regulations, authorities, and processes. Integrating spatial plans into a package in the LADM is essential to ensure that stakeholders have the complete picture of RRRs of land or space</i></p>
ISO/DIS 19152-1	<p>Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 1: Generic Conceptual Model</p>	<p><i>This document:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>defines a reference Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) covering basic information-related</i> - <i>components of land administration/georegulation;</i> - <i>provides an abstract, conceptual model with packages related to:</i> - <i>parties (people and organizations);</i> - <i>basic administrative units, rights, responsibilities, and restrictions;</i> - <i>spatial units.</i> - <i>provides terminology for land administration/georegulation, based on various national and international systems, that is as simple as possible in order to be useful in practice. The terminology allows a shared description of different formal or informal practices and procedures in various jurisdictions;</i> - <i>provides a platform for indicators-based comparison and monitoring;</i> - <i>provides a content model independent of encoding, allowing for the support of various encodings;</i> - <i>provides a basis for national and regional profiles;</i> - <i>enables the combining of land administration/georegulation information from different sources in a coherent manner.</i> <p><i>The following are outside the scope of this document:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — <i>interference with (national) land administration/georegulation laws that may have any legal implications;</i>

Reference	Title	Scope
		<p>— construction of external databases with party data, address data, land cover data, physical utility network data, archive data and taxation data. However, the LADM provides stereotype classes for these data sets to indicate which data set elements the LADM expects from these external sources, if available.</p> <p><i>This document provides the concepts and basic structure for standardization in the land administration/georegulation domain. It defines a general schema that permits regulatory information to be described. It also allows for the relationship to multiple parties and groups to be expressed together with a referencing structure so that sourcing of all information systems may be maintained.</i></p> <p><i>This document establishes the common elements and basic schema upon which more detailed schema may be established. Other parts of ISO 19152 will address specific areas of the land administration paradigm building upon the common core schema defined in document.</i></p>
ISO/PWI 19152-6	Geographic information — Land Administration Domain Model (LADM) — Part 6: Part 6: Implementation aspects	--